

Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with 4-Substituted-1-(2-furoyl)thiosemicarbazides[†]

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Metal complexes of the type $MLCl_2$, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ; $L = 1-(2-furoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide$, $1-(2-furoyl)-4-(p-chlorophenyl)thiosemicarbazide$ or $1-(2-furoyl)-4-(p-bromophenyl)thiosemicarbazide$, have been synthesised. Analytical data magnetic moment, molar conductance, electronic and infrared spectral data have been explored to elucidate the structure of the complexes.

THE thiosemicarbazides and their metal complexes are of great importance due to their wide range of analytical and pharmacological applications¹⁻⁴. As ligands, they provide three potential donor sites, viz. O, N and S, and form complexes with various transitional and non-transitional metal ions. The present paper deals with synthesis of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of 1-(2-furoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (L), 1-(2-furoyl)-4-(*p*-chlorophenyl)thiosemicarbazide (L') and 1-(2-furoyl)-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)thiosemicarbazide (L'') and their characterisation with the aid of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, molar conductance, ir and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligands L, L' and L'' were synthesised by the literature methods⁵.

Preparation of complexes: A hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.05 M) was treated with metal chloride (0.05 M) in the same solvent with vigorous stirring. The resulting reddish brown solution was refluxed for about 30 min, a saturated ethanolic solution of sodium acetate was then added dropwise to the reaction mixture to raise the pH to 5-6 (except for Cu^{II} complexes) and the reflux continued for a few minutes. The solution was concentrated and treated with an excess of distilled water to get the complexes separated as insoluble residue. These were filtered, washed with little ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride. The complexes are brown, reddish brown or green coloured amorphous solids stable in air, and soluble in DMF, DMSO and pyridine.

The metal, nitrogen, sulphur and chloride were estimated by standard methods. The results of analyses are shown in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The measurements of molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared spectra and electronic spectra (nujol) were made as detailed in our earlier paper⁶. The electronic spectra of the complexes in pyridine solution were recorded in the range 900-340 nm on Elico model CL-24 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were of 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry (Table 1). The molar conductances in DMF ($10^{-3}M$) were in the range $6-31 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ suggesting non-electrolytic⁷ nature of the complexes.

The μ_{eff} values (Table 1) for Co^{II} complexes are in the range 2.48-2.7 B.M. which are well within the range expected for square-planar Co^{II} complexes⁸. For Cu^{II} complexes, the observed values (Table 1) lie in the range 1.65-1.79 B.M. which correspond to square-planar geometry. The subnormal values may be ascribed to the spin-orbit coupling taking place by super-exchange through the bridging sulphur atoms⁹ or metal-metal interaction in the dimeric or polymeric structure formed through halogen bridging¹⁰. Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature suggesting their square-planar stereochemistry¹¹.

The solid state electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit two prominent bands, one of medium intensity at $14\ 290-16\ 390 cm^{-1}$ and the second of high intensity at $18\ 180-19\ 610 cm^{-1}$, attributable to ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{1g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^4E_g$ transitions, respectively in square-planar geometry¹². The relatively high intensity of the second band may be due to contributions by the charge transfer transition appearing in the region $28\ 570-30\ 000 cm^{-1}$. In pyridine solution, the Co^{II} complexes exhibit only one band at $18\ 500-20\ 000 cm^{-1}$, as a shoulder on a steeply raising uv

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	N	S	OI		
CoLCl ₂	Dark brown	255	15.60 (15.07)	10.60 (10.74)	8.72 (8.18)	18.89 (18.17)	30.5	2.48
NiLCl ₂	Light brown	285	15.82 (15.02)	10.61 (10.75)	8.00 (8.19)	17.93 (18.71)	20.83	—
CuI Cl ₂	Brown	195	16.85 (16.05)	10.12 (10.62)	7.88 (8.09)	17.85 (17.95)	18.18	1.68
CoL'Cl ₂	Dark green	240	13.29 (13.82)	9.20 (9.86)	7.25 (7.51)	15.34 (16.67)	28.50	2.59
NiL'Cl ₂	Light brown	255	13.61 (13.80)	9.67 (9.88)	7.62 (7.58)	16.43 (16.70)	6.15	—
CuL'Cl ₂	Dark brown	180	14.80 (14.75)	9.65 (9.75)	6.88 (7.48)	16.89 (16.49)	30.85	1.65
CoL''Cl ₂	Brown	260	12.25 (12.52)	8.55 (8.94)	6.62 (6.81)	15.01 (15.11)	25.15	2.70
NiL''Cl ₂	Reddish brown	300	12.31 (12.49)	8.77 (8.94)	6.70 (6.81)	15.41 (15.12)	12.61	—
CuL''Cl ₂	Green	190	13.55 (13.98)	8.45 (8.85)	6.12 (6.74)	14.56 (14.96)	23.35	1.79

absorption tail of a charge transfer band. Hence, the change of absorption bands and absence of any band around $15\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribed to the change of geometry from planar to pseudo-octahedral ones.

The diamagnetic Ni^{II} complexes exhibit a medium intensity band at $16\,130\text{--}16\,673 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a high intensity band at $23\,810\text{--}30\,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to transitions from ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^1E_g$, respectively¹³. The high intensity of the latter band may be due to overlap of L→M charge transfer band. The Ni^{II} complexes undergo colour change from brown to yellow in pyridine thereby showing new uv absorption bands at $13\,420\text{--}14\,390$ and $24\,690\text{--}26\,315 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which correspond to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_2)$ transition, respectively in an octahedral stereochemistry, with the disappearance of bands observed in the solid state spectra. The band due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$ transition could not be located due to instrumental limitation. However, the values of ν_1 band have been computed ($8\,100\text{--}8\,600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The calculated values of Racah parameter, B ($981\text{--}993 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the ratio ν_2/ν_1 (1.65–1.67) for the complexes in pyridine are well within the range expected for pseudo-octahedral Ni^{II} complexes¹³. It may be concluded that the square-planar Ni^{II} complexes have undergone an axial addition of two pyridine molecules to form pseudo-octahedral structure by expanding the coordination number from four to six¹⁴. A single broad band ($15\,380\text{--}21\,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes (in the solid state) is well in the range for square-planar complexes. The three transitions, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, $\rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and $\rightarrow {}^2E_g$ are very close in energy and form a single broad band¹⁵. The absence of any band below $10\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ rules out the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral geometry¹⁵. The high intense band observed at $25\,000\text{--}31\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is ascribed to L→M charge transfer transition. Only one medium intensity band is observed at $12\,820\text{--}16\,130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes in pyridine

solution and no band is observed around $18\,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The 10Dq values calculated for the spectra in pyridine lie in the range $1\,430\text{--}1\,560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This implies that the square-planar configuration has changed in pyridine, thus suggesting coordination of two solvent molecules forming pseudo-octahedral structure¹⁶.

The infrared bands for the free ligands in the region $3\,230\text{--}3\,125 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to intermolecularly hydrogen bonded NH stretch^{17,18}. In the metal complexes the NH bands undergo positive shift or remain unaltered, suggesting the non-involvement of NH group in bonding with metal ion. The N–N stretching bands¹⁹ ($950\text{--}920 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the ligands show red shift in the complexes suggesting that protonation has not been possible to N–N group and no coordination has taken place through NH group²⁰. In the complexes, the C=O stretching bands of the ligand ($1\,650\text{--}1\,610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) show red-shift of $10\text{--}55 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes suggesting the participation of C=O group in coordination²¹. The ligands exist in thione and keto form since no bands due to SH and OH stretch are observed in the region $2\,600\text{--}2\,400$ and $3\,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The ligand bands observed at $1\,295\text{--}1\,255 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribed to C–O–C (furan ring) stretching vibration^{5,22}. These bands show blue-shifts in the respective complexes suggesting the non-involvement of furan ring oxygen in bonding. The ligand bands observed at $1\,555\text{--}1\,500$, $1\,390\text{--}1\,350$, $1\,080\text{--}1\,025$ and $790\text{--}730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to the thioamide bands I, II, III and IV, respectively^{17,23}. On complexation the thioamide band I remains unaltered or show slight blue- or red-shift, since it has major contribution of NH deform and small contribution of C–N stretch. The thioamide bands II and III with some contributions of C=S stretch in the complexes have shown lower frequency shift of the order of $5\text{--}30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with varying intensity. The thioamide band IV mainly due to C=S stretch has shown considerable red-shift with reduced intensity in all the complexes suggest-

ing the coordination of thioketo sulphur²⁴. The 500-370 cm^{-1} bands in the far-ir region are attributed to M-O (carbonyl) stretching vibration in the complexes²⁵. In all the complexes, the medium intensity bands observed at 280-220 cm^{-1} are ascribed to M-Cl stretching mode²⁶. The bands observed in the region 270-225 cm^{-1} are attributed to M-S stretching mode²⁷. The M-S stretching mode appears in the vicinity of M-Cl stretch where there is possibility of both vibrations to overlap. The reduced intensity of M-O and M-S stretching modes may be due to the polymeric nature of the complexes²⁸.

It is, therefore, evident that the ligands exhibit bidentate nature in all the complexes by bonding through the carbonyl oxygen and thioketo sulphur atoms as shown in the following structure.

where, $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Cu^{II} ; $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}(p)$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}(p)$.

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